

Pronounced surface enrichment of fluorinated ionic liquids in binary mixtures with methoxy-functionalized ionic liquids

Bettina S.J. Heller, Ulrike Paap, Florian Maier, Hans-Peter Steinrück*

Lehrstuhl für Physikalische Chemie II, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Egerlandstraße 3, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Different binary mixtures of two functionalized ionic liquids (ILs), namely 1,3-di(methoxy)imidazolium hexafluorophosphate, [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], and 3-methyl-1-(3,3,4,4,4-pentafluorobutyl)imidazolium hexafluorophosphate, [PFBMIm][PF₆], are investigated in the liquid state by angle-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (ARXPS). Both ILs consist of the same [PF₆][−] anion but differ in the functionalization of the cation: [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] has an oxygen atom directly bound to each nitrogen atom of the imidazolium ring whereas in [PFBMIm][PF₆] the two terminal carbon atoms of the butyl chain are fully fluorinated. Due to different electronic structures of the cations of both ILs, the ARXP signals of the two cations and of the anion can be well distinguished, which allows to identify preferential chain orientation as well as enrichment and depletion effects at the surface. In the mixtures with 50, 90 and 95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], a very pronounced enrichment of the [PFBMIm]⁺ cation at the IL/vacuum interface is observed. The fluorinated chain points towards the vacuum side and thereby attenuates the signal of the [PF₆][−] anion. Decreasing the temperature from 95 °C to close to the solidification temperatures of the mixtures leads to a more pronounced surface enrichment of the [PFBMIm]⁺ cation and of the fluorinated chain.

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1. Introduction

Ionic liquids (ILs), salts with melting points typically below 100 °C, are nowadays used in many applications like lubrication [1–3], gas separation [4,5], extraction [6–9], energy storage [2,10] and catalysis [3,11,12], due to their unique physico-chemical properties such as their very low vapor pressure. By introducing functional groups into the IL ions or by combining various anions and cations in IL mixtures, the specific properties of the IL system can be well adapted to the respective technical requirements [6,11,13,14]. In many of the aforementioned applications, the interface of the IL and the gas phase plays a significant role, in particular for new catalysis concepts using thin films of ILs on high surface-area supports, such as Supported Ionic Liquid Phase (SILP) [15–17] materials and Solid Catalyst with Ionic Liquid Layer (SCILL) [16,18] systems. The composition of the outermost IL surface layer can be very different to the bulk composition. The thermodynamic driving force to minimize surface free energy can lead to preferential enrichment and depletion effects [19]. Moreover, some functional groups exhibit pronounced orientation effects in the outermost layer [20]. Investigating the IL/gas-vacuum interface is thus of high relevance from a fundamental point of view, in order to obtain an atomistic understanding of molecular liquid surfaces. This knowledge

will then allow for optimizing the performance of IL systems in specific applications.

For this reason, several investigations of IL mixtures [21], have been carried out using surface-sensitive techniques – often under ultra-high vacuum (UHV) conditions – such as reactive-atom scattering-laser-induced fluorescence (RAS-LIF) [22,23], time-of-flight secondary mass spectrometry (TOF-SIMS) [24,25], low-energy ion scattering (LEIS) [26], X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) [27–34], Rutherford backscattering spectroscopy (RBS) [25,35–37], metastable induced electron spectroscopy (MIES) [38] and simulations [14,22,23,33,36,39–42]. Most of these studies addressed mixtures of non-functionalized ILs, with only a few including also functionalized ILs. We therefore set out to perform a detailed, temperature-dependent study of IL mixtures containing two functionalized ILs.

Among the many known functional moieties in ILs, alkoxy groups are of high interest. It is generally known that functionalization with oxygen atoms, that is, ester, ether or hydroxyl, often decreases the toxicity of the IL and also improves biodegradability [43,44]. Due to their ether group, additional hydrogen bond acceptor sites are present in alkoxy-functionalized ILs, which leads to interesting properties [6,45]. Alkoxy-functionalization at the imidazolium ring allows for, e.g. the transformation into N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) and eventually into organometallic moieties for IL-based organometallic catalysis [45–47]. By adding unsaturated substituents to the oxygen atom, a selective extraction of metals has been proposed [45]. Alkoxy-functionalized ILs are also

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: hans-peter.steinrueck@fau.de (H.-P. Steinrück).

able to dissolve greenhouse gases like CO₂ [48] and N₂O [49] as well as being used in liquid-phase microextraction of analgesics (e.g. ibuprofen) and estrogens from aqueous samples [6].

As one of the first surface science studies of functionalized/non-functionalized IL mixtures, we investigated the IL/vacuum interface of the alkoxy IL 1,3-di(methoxy)imidazolium hexafluorophosphate [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆]; see Fig. 1) and its equimolar mixtures with non-functionalized ILs such as 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium bis[(trifluoromethyl)sulfonyl]imide, [C₈C₁Im][Tf₂N], and 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate, [C₈C₁Im][PF₆], using angle-resolved XPS (ARXPS) and density functional theory (DFT) [27]. DFT showed that the electronic structure of the [(MeO)₂Im]⁺ cation differs considerably from that of the non-functionalized [C₈C₁Im]⁺ cation: Due to the electron withdrawing oxygen atoms next to the imidazolium nitrogen atoms, the ring of [(MeO)₂Im]⁺ is more positively charged, which was confirmed by the fact that the N 1s core level are strongly shifted to higher binding energy by more than 1 eV. This pronounced shift enables a clear distinction of the methoxy-functionalized and the non-functionalized cations. In the mixtures, a surface depletion of the [(MeO)₂Im]⁺ cation relative to the [C₈C₁Im]⁺ cation and a surface enrichment of the [Tf₂N]⁻ anion relative to the [PF₆]⁻ anion was deduced. These deviations from the bulk compositions were attributed to the differences in surface tension of the neat ILs.

Very recently, our group published the results of ARXPS investigations on the IL/vacuum interface of the fluorine-functionalized IL 3-methyl-1-(3,3,4,4,4-pentafluorobutyl)imidazolium hexafluorophosphate ([PFBMIm][PF₆]; see Fig. 1) and of its mixtures with the non-functionalized counterpart IL 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate, [C₄C₁Im][PF₆] [28]. A pronounced surface enrichment of the partially fluorinated chain with respect to the fully hydrogenated butyl chain was found at 95 °C. With decreasing temperature and with decreasing content of [PFBMIm][PF₆], the enrichment effects were observed to be more pronounced. One drawback of this study was related to the difficulty to distinguish the imidazolium head groups by XPS because of the virtually identical imidazolium ring signals.

The data presented herein show for the first time the influence of two different functional groups on the surface composition of IL

Fig. 1. Structure of 1,3-di(methoxy)imidazolium hexafluorophosphate, [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], (top) and 3-methyl-1-(3,3,4,4,4-pentafluorobutyl)imidazolium hexafluorophosphate, [PFBMIm][PF₆], (bottom). The peak assignment in the C 1s spectra of the C₂, C_{hetero'} and C_{CF_x} is indicated in gray.

mixtures, as a function of bulk composition and temperature. Furthermore, due to the different electronic structures of [(MeO)₂Im]⁺ and [PFBMIm]⁺, with well-separated signals in the N 1s spectra, simultaneous information acquisition about the side chains in the cations and the related cationic head groups is possible by ARXPS. In comparison to the previous study [28], we find a much more pronounced enrichment of the cations with the fluorinated chain.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

[PFBMIm][PF₆] and [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] were synthesized as published earlier [47,50,51]. No further purification of the ILs was carried out prior to the investigations. For the preparation of the mixtures with 50, 90 and 95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], acetonitrile from Sigma-Aldrich (purity 99.8%) was used as a co-solvent to ensure proper mixing of [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] and [PFBMIm][PF₆]. The mixtures as well as the neat ILs were placed on a molybdenum sample holder with a thickness up to 0.5 mm. Degassing of the samples was carried out in the load-lock of our vacuum chamber for at least 12 h. Samples were measured under UHV conditions in the liquid state at 95 °C and lower temperatures till solidification occurred.

2.2. Angle-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

The ARXPS measurements were performed with a monochromated Al K_α X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) at a power of 238 W. The data was acquired with two identical hemispherical ARGUS-type analyzers which are mounted at $\theta = 0^\circ$ (normal emission) and 80° (grazing emission) with respect to the surface normal of a horizontally mounted sample. For more details see Ref. [52]. High-resolution spectra were recorded with a pass energy of 35 eV resulting in an energy resolution of 0.4 eV. The Fermi level of a polycrystalline Au sample was used to reference the binding energy of all spectra. Small deviations from sample to sample (± 0.2 eV) did not affect the results discussed here, and thus no corrections were applied. At lower temperatures, shifts to higher binding energies were used to detect sample solidification by XPS as has been done before [28]. For the temperature-dependent measurements, the temperature was measured directly at the molybdenum reservoir filled with IL with an accuracy of ± 5 °C [53].

Depending on the kinetic energy, the information depth of XPS in organic matter is 7 to 9 nm in 0° emission. At an emission angle of 80° , it decreases by about a factor of six, resulting in a more surface-sensitive measurement of the first 1 to 1.5 nm. To allow for visualizing enrichment/depletion effects through direct comparison, all 80° measurements were scaled up by an individual geometry factor to account for the overall lower transmission in this geometry (for details see Ref. [52]). Atomic sensitivity factors (ASFs) were applied to enable a quantitative analysis of the individual core levels [52]. The data were analyzed using CasaXPS (version 2.3.16Dev6), and for peak fitting a pseudo-Voigt function with 30% Lorentzian contribution was used. In general, a two-point linear background was subtracted from all spectra except for the C 1s spectra where a three-point linear background was applied. For the mixtures, the full width at half maximum (FWHM) in the N 1s spectra was set equal for the N_{MeO} and N_{PF₆} peaks (for peak assignments, see Fig. 1 and text below), and in the F 1s spectra the FWHM of the F_{PF₆} peak was 0.79 times that of the F_{CF_x} peak. Only for the 95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] mixture with its very small N_{PF₆} intensity, additional constraints were applied for the nitrogen peak separation (1.40 ± 0.04 eV, as deduced from the measurements of the other two mixtures) to obtain unambiguous fitting results. Since the C_{CF₃} peak of the [PFBMIm]⁺ cation in the C 1s spectra overlaps with the shake-up of the C_{hetero'} peak of the imidazolium ring, the CF₃ signal was set equal to the CF₂ signal to quantify the intensity of the first one. The intensity ratio of the C_{hetero'} and C₂ intensities was constraint to the nominal

ratios in the mixtures, e.g. 4:1 for neat $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and 4.5:1 for the 50 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ mixture. For neat $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$, the C_2 and $\text{C}_{\text{hetero}'}$ peak separation was fixed to 1.02 eV, with the FWHM of the latter 1.33 times larger than that of the former. The spin-orbit-split $\text{P } 2\text{p}_{1/2}$ and $\text{P } 2\text{p}_{3/2}$ levels with an intensity ratio of 1:2 have equal FWHM and are separated by 0.9 eV. All XP spectra are normalized to the overall intensity of the $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ measurement to account for small differences in the photon flux of the X-rays during the course of the measurements.

3. Results and discussion

We performed temperature-dependent ARXPS measurements of several mixtures of two ILs, that is, 3-methyl-1-(3,3,4,4,4-pentafluorobutyl)imidazolium hexafluorophosphate, $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$, and 1,3-di(methoxy)imidazolium hexafluorophosphate, $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$; see Fig. 1. We will present data for three mixtures with 50, 90 and 95 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$. As reference data, we will also briefly address the spectra of the neat ILs which have been published recently [27,28]. The two ILs consist of the same $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ anion, but differ in the

functionalization of their cation. To ensure measurements in the liquid state, the starting temperature was 95 °C (90 °C for $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ in Ref. [27]), because the melting point of neat $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ are 66 [50] and 83–84 °C, respectively [27]. In the following, we first present the spectra at 95 °C in detail, followed by the discussion of the temperature-dependent behavior (down to the different solidification temperatures as lowest limit). We will particularly focus on enrichment and depletion effects.

3.1. ARXPS measurements at 95 °C

We first address the spectra of the neat ILs. The F 1s spectrum of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ in Fig. 2a (left panel) shows two distinct peaks. The F_{CF_x} peak at 688.9 eV results from the fluorine atoms in the CF_2 and CF_3 groups in the fluorinated chain of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation, and the F_{PF_6} peak at 686.8 eV from the $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ anion. The comparison of the spectra in the two experimental geometries reveals an increase of the F_{CF_x} intensity and a decrease of the F_{PF_6} intensity at 80° compared to 0°. This behavior indicates an enrichment of the fluorinated chain due to a preferential orientation towards the vacuum side, and simultaneously

Fig. 2. F 1s (left), N 1s (center) and C 1s (right) spectra, at 0° (black) and 80° (red) emission: a) Neat $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$, b) – d) mixtures of $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ at molar ratios of b) 50 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$, c) 90 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and d) 95 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$, and e) neat $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$. All spectra were acquired at a sample temperature of 95 °C and are normalized to the overall intensity of $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ to compensate for differences in X-ray flux.

a depletion of the $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ anion, at the outermost surface. This surface enrichment of the fluorinated chain is also evident in the C 1s region (right panel) through the higher 80° intensity of the C_{CF_2} and C_{CF_3} peaks at 291.3 and 293.6 eV, respectively. Notably, this effect is less pronounced than for the F_{CF_x} signal due to the higher kinetic energy (1200 vs. 800 eV for F 1s) and consequently higher inelastic mean free path of the emitted C 1s electrons. In contrast, the C 1s and N 1s signals from the imidazolium head group, that is, C_{hetero} at 286.8 eV and C_2 at 287.8 eV (for assignment see Fig. 1) and N_{PF_6} at 402.2 eV, show a lower signal at 80° than at 0° . The same is true for the P_{PF_6} peak of the $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ anion, which is centered at 137.0 eV (Figs. S1a and S2). The decrease of these peaks at 80° is explained by the enrichment of the fluorinated chain of the $[\text{PF}_6\text{BIm}]^+$ cation at the IL/vacuum interface, which leads to an attenuation of the signals from species underneath. Notably, both the quantitative analysis provided in Table 1a, and the absence of any detectable signals of common surface active impurities in the O 1s and Si 2p regions (Figs. S1a and S2) confirm a high purity of $[\text{PF}_6\text{BIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ within the detection limits of XPS [20].

Next, we discuss the ARXP spectra of neat $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ in Fig. 2e, measured at 95°C , which are virtually identical to those reported at 90°C [27]. In the F 1s region (left panel), the F_{PF_6} peak of the $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ anion is located at 686.5 eV; the corresponding P_{PF_6} peak in the P 2p region is located at 136.7 eV (see Figs. S1e and S3). The peaks of the $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}]^+$ cation are detected at the following energies: O_{MeO} at 535.0 eV, N_{MeO} at 403.3 eV, C_2 at 287.8 eV and C_{hetero} at 286.7 eV. Notably, the N_{MeO} signal of $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ is located at +1.1 eV higher binding energy than the N_{PF_6} signal of $[\text{PF}_6\text{BIm}][\text{PF}_6]$, which is due to a difference in the electronic structure of the cations as shown by DFT calculations combined with atomic charge analysis by our group [27]. This difference in N 1s binding energy allows for unambiguous identification and analysis of surface enrichment/depletion effects of the cationic head groups in the mixtures by ARXPS. The comparison of the neat $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ spectra recorded in 0° and 80° emission shows no difference in the F 1s region and only minor differences in the N 1s and C 1s peak areas (Table 1e), indicating the absence of significant

surface enrichment or depletion for any part of $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$. Again, the good agreement of the quantitative analysis in Table 1e and the absence of any detectable signals in the Si 2p region (Figs. S1e and S3) confirms a high purity of this IL within the detection limits of XPS [20].

After discussing the two neat ILs, we turn to mixtures of $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[\text{PF}_6\text{BIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ in three different compositions, with 50, 90 and 95 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$. In the analysis of the spectra, we are particularly interested in obtaining information about selective enrichment/depletion of the cations in those mixtures. The F 1s, N 1s and C 1s spectra measured at a temperature of 95°C are shown in Fig. 2b – 2d, and in Figs. S4, S5 and S6; spectra in black are measured at 0° , spectra in red at 80° emission angle. The corresponding O 1s and P 2p regions are shown in Fig. S1b – S1d, and in Figs. S4, S5 and S6. The binding energy positions of the peaks in the mixtures are in accordance with the peak positions detected in the neat ILs to within ± 0.2 eV. In the F 1s region (Fig. 2b – 2d-left panel), two peaks are detected. The F_{CF_x} peak at ~ 688.8 eV solely stems from the fluorinated chain of the $[\text{PF}_6\text{BIm}]^+$ cation of one IL, and the F_{PF_6} peak at ~ 686.6 eV is due to the common $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ anion of both ILs in the mixture. The decreasing intensity of the F_{CF_x} peak at 0° upon increasing the $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}]^+$ content from 0 mol% (a), to 50 mol% (b), to 90 mol% (c) and finally to 95 mol% (d) reflects the decreasing $[\text{PF}_6\text{BIm}]^+$ content of the mixtures. Interestingly, the decrease of the F_{CF_x} peak is much less pronounced at 80° : Relative to the intensities measured in 0° , the 80° spectra of the 50, 90 and 95 mol% mixtures show an increase of the F_{CF_x} intensity by a factor of 1.68, 2.55 and 2.87, respectively, which indicates a selective surface enrichment of the cation with the fluorinated chain. At the same time, the relative intensity of the F_{PF_6} peak decreases by a factor of 0.75, 0.81 and 0.86 in 80° for the 50, 90 and 95 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ mixtures, respectively. This decrease is attributed to the preferential orientation of the fluorinated chain towards the vacuum side, and the resulting attenuation of the $[\text{PF}_6]^-$ signal relative to the bulk composition. This effect was already observed for neat $[\text{PF}_6\text{BIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ and is maintained in the mixtures.

Table 1
Quantitative analysis of the 0° and 80° XP spectra of $[\text{PF}_6\text{BIm}][\text{PF}_6]$, $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and their mixtures with 50, 90 and 95 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ at 95°C . The ASFs are taken into account as published earlier [52].

a) $[\text{PF}_6\text{BIm}][\text{PF}_6]$	F 1s F_{CF_x}	F 1s F_{PF_6}	O 1s O_{MeO}	N 1s N_{MeO}	N 1s N_{PF_6}	C 1s C_{CF_x}	C 1s C_2	C 1s C_{hetero}	P 2p P_{PF_6}
Binding Energy/eV	688.9	686.8	—/—	—/—	402.2	291.3/293.6	287.8	286.8	137.0
ASF	1.00	1.00	0.67	0.46	0.46	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.46
Nominal	5.00	6.00	—/—	—/—	2.00	2.00	1.00	5.00	1.00
0° emission	5.55	5.99	—/—	—/—	1.93	1.84	0.99	4.61	1.08
80° emission	7.04	5.00	—/—	—/—	1.69	2.12	1.03	4.14	0.99
b) 50 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$	F_{CF_x}	F_{PF_6}	O_{MeO}	N_{MeO}	N_{PF_6}	C_{CF_x}	C_2	C_{hetero}	P_{PF_6}
Nominal	2.89	6.94	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16	5.20	1.16
0° emission	3.71	6.84	0.97	0.97	1.26	1.16	1.06	4.78	1.21
80° emission	6.25	5.17	0.50	0.53	1.30	1.82	0.96	4.34	1.09
c) 90 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$	F_{CF_x}	F_{PF_6}	O_{MeO}	N_{MeO}	N_{PF_6}	C_{CF_x}	C_2	C_{hetero}	P_{PF_6}
Nominal	0.66	7.95	2.38	2.38	0.26	0.26	1.32	5.43	1.32
0° emission	1.55	7.91	2.13	2.05	0.45	0.38	1.20	4.9	1.41
80° emission	3.97	6.47	1.43	1.38	0.80	1.04	1.10	4.53	1.27
d) 95 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$	F_{CF_x}	F_{PF_6}	O_{MeO}	N_{MeO}	N_{PF_6}	C_{CF_x}	C_2	C_{hetero}	P_{PF_6}
Nominal	0.34	8.10	2.56	2.56	0.13	0.14	1.35	5.47	1.35
0° emission	0.93	8.14	2.47	2.33	0.20	0.16	1.25	5.06	1.46
80° emission	2.68	7.03	1.90	1.78	0.52	0.62	1.20	4.88	1.39
e) $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]^a$	F_{CF_x}	F_{PF_6}	O_{MeO}	N_{MeO}	N_{PF_6}	C_{CF_x}	C_2	C_{hetero}	P_{PF_6}
Binding Energy/eV	—/—	686.5	535.0	403.3	—/—	—/—	287.8	286.7	136.7
Nominal	—/—	6.00	2.00	2.00	—/—	—/—	1.00	4.00	1.00
0° emission	—/—	6.29	2.03	1.90	—/—	—/—	0.93	3.73	1.10
80° emission	—/—	6.30	2.04	1.86	—/—	—/—	0.93	3.72	1.15

^a Note that the binding energies of all core levels are by 0.3 eV smaller than those in Ref. [27].

In the N 1s region of the three mixtures, we observe two peaks, the N_{MeO} peak due to the $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}]^+$ cation at ~ 403.5 eV, and the N_{PFB} peak due to the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation at ~ 402.1 eV. In the mixture with 50 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$, the intensities of the N_{PFB} peak at 0° and 80° emission are identical within the margin of error, whereas the intensity of the N_{MeO} peak is by a factor of 0.55 smaller at 80° . These relative intensities contain information about the position of the cationic head groups of the two ILs in the mixture relative to each other. From the observed behavior, we conclude that the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation is preferentially located closer to the IL/vacuum interface compared to the $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}]^+$ cation, which is in line with the surface enrichment of the fluorinated chains discussed above.

We attribute the observed surface enrichment behavior in the mixtures to the fact that the system tries to minimize its surface free energy. As shown recently by a comparative ARXPS and molecular dynamic simulation study [54], groups generally lowering the surface tension for ILs such as long alkyl chains [55] are preferentially surface-enriched whereas groups leading to an increase in surface tension are surface-depleted. Typically, ILs with a fluorinated chain exhibit a lower surface tension compared to their alkylated IL counterparts [22,42]. This is underlined by the surface enrichment of the fluorinated chains of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cations with respect to the butyl chains recently deduced by ARXPS for mixtures of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ [28]. Unfortunately, the exact surface tension values of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ are not known yet at any temperatures. It is nevertheless reasonable to assume that the former has a lower surface tension than the latter. At least what is known for imidazolium cations containing oxygen is that the surface tension of a polyethylene glycol IL, $[\text{Me}(\text{EG})_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TF}_2\text{N}]$, with two oxygen atoms in the side chain is larger than the surface tension of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TF}_2\text{N}]$ [56], which is in line with our argumentation.

For the 90 and 95 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ mixtures, we find the same trend as for the 50 mol% mixture, but the enrichment/depletion effects are more pronounced. With respect to the bulk composition, we see an increase of the N_{PFB} signal by a factor of 1.78 and 2.65, respectively, when going from 0° to 80° , while the N_{MeO} signal decreases by a factor of 0.67 and 0.76, respectively. Remarkably, (without applying any constraints) the depletion behavior of the O_{MeO} peak is identical to that of the N_{MeO} signal (to within 3%), indicating a reliability of our measurements because these two atoms are directly bound to each other. The surface enrichment of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation with its fluorinated chain is also evident from the C 1s spectra: The intensities of the C_{CF_3} and C_{CF_2} peaks also strongly increase when changing the detection angle from 0° to 80° emission. The other two signals of the IL mixtures, that is, $\text{C}_2 + \text{C}_{\text{hetero}}$ and P_{PF_6} , are damped by up to 10% due to the attenuation by the surface-enriched fluorinated chain. The pronounced enrichment and depletion of the ions in the mixtures can also be deduced from the quantitative analysis of all signals in Table 1b–d.

For further analysis of the enrichment/depletion of the different cations in the mixture, we plotted the normalized content, that is, the ratio of the experimentally determined content and the nominal content (see Table 1) in Fig. 3a for 80° emission. A value of 1.0 represents the situation, where the surface composition is identical to that in the bulk, a value larger than 1.0 indicates surface enrichment of the respective atom. The red squares represent the normalized F_{CF_x} content of the fluorinated chain of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation. The higher the mole fraction of $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ in the mixture, the higher is the normalized F_{CF_x} content, and thus the surface enrichment of the fluorinated chain. The same trend, but less pronounced holds true for the N_{PFB} content (blue triangles), which reflects the enrichment of the whole $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation since the N_{PFB} signal originates from the cationic head group. In contrast, the normalized N_{MeO} content (orange diamonds) is below the nominal ratio, indicating a depletion of the $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}]^+$ cation from the surface. The graph also contains the normalized F_{PF_6} content (green circles) representing all anions in the mixtures. The normalized F_{PF_6} ratio is close to the nominally expected ratio included as gray

Fig. 3. a) Normalized content of F_{CF_x} (red squares), F_{PF_6} (green circles), N_{PFB} (blue triangles) and N_{MeO} (orange diamonds). b) Ratio of the normalized F_{CF_x} and F_{PF_6} contents (full symbols) and ratio of the normalized N_{PFB} and N_{MeO} content (open symbols) at 0° (black) and 80° (red). The sample temperature was 95°C . The dashed gray lines indicate the nominal ratios.

dashed line. This is not unexpected due to charge neutrality reasons: Each imidazolium ring is preferentially located close to the counter anion. The F_{PF_6} signal thus represents in a first approximation the mean localization of the charged head groups.

In Fig. 3b, we thus plot the ratio of the normalized F_{CF_x} and F_{PF_6} signals (full symbols; from Fig. 3a) vs. the mole fraction of the ILs (top scale for mole fraction of $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}]^+$, bottom scale for mole fraction of $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$) for the 0° (black squares) and the 80° (red diamonds) data. Notably, for neat $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$, the value of ~ 1.8 at 80° as compared to ~ 1.1 at 0° reflects the preferential orientation of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cations with the fluorinated chains pointing towards the vacuum in the outermost surface layer. Larger ratio values than 1.8 in the mixtures indicate an enrichment of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cations with their fluorinated chains by preferential surface segregation at the cost of the $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}]^+$ cations. At 80° emission, we find values of ~ 2.9 , ~ 7.4 and ~ 9.2 for the mixtures with 50, 90 and 95 mol% $[(\text{MeO})_2\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$, respectively, which indicates an increasingly pronounced surface enrichment of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation (relative to its concentration in the bulk). In our previous work [28], we investigated mixtures of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$, which also showed an enrichment of the fluorinated chain of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation compared to the $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}]^+$ cation. However, the enrichment effects were much less pronounced, that is, for a mixture with 90 mol% $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ a ratio of the normalized F_{CF_x} and F_{PF_6} contents of ~ 3.5 was observed (as compared to ~ 7.4 here) at 80° emission angle and a temperature of 95°C [28]. Notably, the very pronounced surface enrichment of the $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ cation for the 90 and

95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] mixtures can even be observed in the much more bulk-sensitive 0° geometry, where XPS integrates over the first 7 to 9 nm (see Fig. 3b), as shown for different systems by our group and others [27,28,33].

The ratios of the normalized N_{PFB} and N_{MeO} contents along with the nominal value (gray dashed line) are shown in Fig. 3b (open symbols). Overall, we observe the same trend as for the F_{CFX} and F_{PF6} data. This behavior confirms that with higher [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] content a more pronounced enrichment of the [PFBMIm]⁺ cation occurs compared to the [(MeO)₂Im]⁺ cation, which means that the [PFBMIm]⁺ cation is located closer to the IL/vacuum interface than the other head group. Interestingly, the effect of surface enrichment is less pronounced than for the

F_{CFX} and F_{PF6} data (i.e. at 90 mol% the ratio is ~5.2 instead of ~7.4 for the latter). This is attributed to the fact that the N_{PFB} and N_{MeO} show only the effect of the relative enrichment of the cations, whereas the F_{CFX} and F_{PF6} data include the preferential enrichment of the fluorinated chain (see above).

3.2. Temperature-dependent ARXPS

After having discussed the results at the highest temperature of 95 °C, we now address the temperature-dependent XP spectra, starting with the two neat ILs during cooling to the onset of solidification. Since changes in enrichment and depletion are more obvious at 80° electron

Fig. 4. F 1s, N 1s and C 1s spectra measured at 80° emission during cooling from 95 °C to lower temperatures: a) Neat [PFBMIm][PF₆], b) – d) mixtures of [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] and [PFBMIm][PF₆] at molar ratios of b) 50 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], c) 90 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] and d) 95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], and e) neat [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆]. The intensities are normalized to the overall intensity of [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] to compensate for differences in X-ray flux.

emission, we focus from here on only on these surface-sensitive spectra. First, we summarize the cooling experiments of [PFBIMIm][PF₆] from 95 °C to its onset of solidification around 20 °C, which have been described in more detail elsewhere [28]. Note the solidification occurs significantly below the melting point of 66 °C [50], which is indicative of a supercooling. In the left panel of Fig. 4a, decreasing the temperature leaves the F_{CFX} signal almost unchanged, whereas the F_{PF6} signal decreases significantly. The resulting relative increase of the F_{CFX} intensity compared to the F_{PF6} intensity upon lowering the temperature (see Fig. 5a) is attributed to a more pronounced orientation of the fluorinated side chains towards the vacuum side, with the polar head groups more confined underneath. This interpretation is confirmed by a

Fig. 5. Ratio of the normalized F_{CFX} and F_{PF6} content, at 0° (black squares) and 80° (red circles) emission, obtained during cooling from 95 °C to lower temperatures. a) Neat [PFBIMIm][PF₆], b) – d) mixtures of [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] and [PFBIMIm][PF₆] at molar ratios of b) 50 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], c) 90 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] and d) 95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], and e) neat [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆]; Not shown due to the lack of F_{CFX} signal of a fluorinated side chain. The dashed horizontal lines indicate the nominal composition.

concomitant small decrease in N_{PF6} and C_{hetero} intensity originating from the cationic head group (see Fig. 4a-middle and right panels). It should be mentioned that a small shoulder at lower binding energies evolves in the C 1s and N 1s region at lower temperatures due to some beam damage [57,58] of the IL by the extended X-ray exposure, which does not affect the conclusions derived here. The overall small shift of all peaks to higher binding energy upon cooling is attributed to the onset of charging in the supercooled phase, which starts already at around 60 °C.

Similar to [PFBIMIm][PF₆], neat [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] can be supercooled well below its melting point without pronounced charging effects due to solidification. In Fig. 4e, selected spectra from 95 °C down to 50 °C are shown; note that beam damage effects become also visible at lower temperatures by a second peak arising in the N 1s spectra (see Fig. S7e-middle panel). Apart from this effect, no significant intensity changes with decreasing temperature are seen in the F 1s, N 1s and C 1s regions. Hence, no significant preferential orientation occurs in the surface layer of [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] even at 50 °C. Note that a moderate shift towards lower binding energies takes place (overall –0.3 eV between the 95 and 50 °C spectra), which is attributed to the beam damage effect mentioned above; when heating the sample back to 95 °C, all peaks shift back to their original binding energy position and the shoulder in the N 1s spectrum is more or less gone.

Finally, we discuss the temperature dependence of the mixtures with 50, 90 and 95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆]. The corresponding F 1s, N 1s and C 1s spectra for selected temperatures are shown in Fig. 4b–d. Depending on the composition of the mixture, the lower temperature limits for XPS measurements of the (supercooled) liquids differ. In general, the lower the [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] content, the lower the solidification temperature, as indicated by the onset of charging of the samples. During cooling down from 95 °C, for all mixtures the enrichment/depletion effects described in the previous section become much more pronounced. In Fig. 5b–d, the quantitative analysis, that is, the ratios of the normalized F_{CFX} and F_{PF6} contents are depicted. While this ratio remains almost constant with decreasing temperature in 0° emission for the three mixtures, in 80° emission it increases significantly. The effect is most pronounced for the mixture with 95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], reaching a value of ~12.2 at 50 °C compared to 9.2 at 95 °C. This is mainly due to an increase of the F_{CFX} intensity and a less pronounced decrease of the F_{PF6} intensity. We observe the same trend in the N 1s region (see Fig. 4b–d-middle panel): The N_{MeO} intensity decreases with decreasing temperature whereas the N_{PF6} signal increases. The ratio of the normalized N_{PF6} and N_{MeO} contents in Fig. 6b–d increases in 80° emission when decreasing the temperature. This again implies the increase of the surface enrichment of the [PFBIMIm]⁺ cation along with a surface depletion of the [(MeO)₂Im]⁺ cation upon cooling the mixtures. In the C 1s region (Fig. 4b–d-right panel), a slight enrichment of the C_{CF2} and C_{CF3} peaks is detected but due to the low mole fraction of [PFBIMIm][PF₆] in the mixtures changes are less obvious than for the F_{CFX} signal.

We attribute the observed overall behavior mostly to entropic reasons. At lower temperature, the enthalpic driving force of surface enrichment of the [PFBIMIm]⁺ cation with its fluorinated chain, which lowers the surface tension of the mixture, dominates. At higher temperatures, the entropic term $-T \cdot \Delta S^\circ$ (note that ΔS° is negative because of the demixing effect by surface enrichment) gains weight and induces a decrease in surface order towards a more random distribution of the [(MeO)₂Im]⁺ and [PFBIMIm]⁺ cations with their fluorinated chains. Thus, when cooling from 95 °C to lower temperature, we observe an increase of surface enrichment due to a smaller entropic contribution to the free energy.

4. Conclusions

We present temperature-dependent angle-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy measurements of mixtures of two functionalized

Fig. 6. Ratio of the normalized N_{PFB} and N_{MeO} content, at 0° (black squares) and 80° (red circles) emission, obtained during cooling from 95 °C to lower temperatures. a) Neat [PFBMIm][PF₆]; Not shown due to the lack of N_{MeO} signal, b) – d) mixtures of [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] and [PFBMIm][PF₆] at molar ratios of b) 50 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], c) 90 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] and d) 95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], and e) neat [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆]; Not shown due to the lack of N_{PFB} signal. The dashed horizontal lines indicate the nominal composition.

ILs with the same [PF₆][−] anion in the liquid state. [PFBMIm][PF₆] is fully fluorinated at the two terminal carbon atoms of the butyl chain whereas [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] contains an oxygen atom next to each nitrogen atom of the imidazolium ring. Measurements were performed for the two neat ILs and for mixtures with 50, 90 and 95 mol% [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], from 95 °C to lower temperatures. While no surface enrichment is observed for neat [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆], a moderate surface enrichment of the fluorinated chain is found for neat [PFBMIm][PF₆], which is attributed to a preferential orientation of the chains towards the vacuum in order to minimize surface free energy. Decreasing the [PFBMIm][PF₆] content in the mixtures by adding more and more [(MeO)₂Im][PF₆] shows a significantly more pronounced enrichment of the fluorinated chain and of the cationic head group of the [PFBMIm]⁺ cation compared to the bulk composition. This strong enrichment is attributed to preferential surface segregation of the [PFBMIm]⁺ cations replacing the [(MeO)₂Im]⁺ cations in this interface region. By decreasing the temperature of the mixtures till solidification is reached, these effects become even more pronounced. Our study shows that the introduction of suitable functional groups in IL molecules for controlling surface activity and the suitable choice of composition using IL mixtures allow for modifying the surface of an IL system to a large extent, which is important for many large-surface area applications involving IL films.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Bettina S.J. Heller: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Ulrike Paap:** Validation, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Florian Maier:** Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Hans-Peter Steinrück:** Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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